

Two Kinds of Uncertainty? Variances and Resolution in Quantum Bound States

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In (1), which deals with entropic uncertainty relationships, it is pointed out that x -variances of quantum bound states may possibly behave in a counterintuitive manner. In particular an example is given of two small boxes attached to the ends of a long pipe centered at zero so the average x is 0. If a particle has a probability of .5 to be in one box or the other a certain variance is found. If the particle can also be anywhere along the pipe or in the boxes the authors of (1) argue there is more uncertainty yet the variance decreases. Mathematically this occurs because there is now probability associated with small x values.

We argue this is only counterintuitive if one considers probability distributions which decrease monotonically such as a Gaussian. In such a case, the variance increases if the particle is spread over a larger range. Such, however, does not seem to be the case if one has increased resolution which seems to be the case for quantum bound states such as a particle in a box with infinite potential walls or a quantum oscillator. Increased resolution occurs with increasing energy, but by the Heisenberg uncertainty principle the variance of p and x (or at least their product) increases. Increased resolution which seems to be linked to more order (less uncertainty) as argued in (1) can lead to an increased variance if probability only exists at distances far from the origin (i.e. high x) as in the closed two boxes example. As a result, the idea of uncertainty in the expression Heisenberg's uncertainty principle seems to be based on the idea of how far the particle may be from the average value. As noted in (1) this means a large variance, but could represent high resolution i.e. a lack of uncertainty in finding the particle.

We suggest there are two different kinds of uncertainty, Heisenberg's uncertainty linked to the average and a resolution uncertainty. We examine the cases of a particle in a box and the quantum oscillator.

Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle

The momentum-position Heisenberg uncertainty principle:

$$\text{Standard deviation } (p) \text{ Standard deviation } (x) \geq \hbar/2 \quad ((1))$$

is based on variances. For simplicity one may consider the origin placed so that $\langle x \rangle = 0$. The word uncertainty is used, but the calculated value is a variance which is a measure of the distance of the particle from the average value. This distance is squared so higher distances are given an even higher weighting. In other words, Heisenberg uncertainty is a measure of deviations from the average value.

In quantum mechanics, it seems this is not the only idea of uncertainty as pointed out in (1). The authors consider two boxes joined by a pipe centered at the origin, but stipulate the particle may only be in one box or the other with a probability of .5. The average value is $x=0$ and a

certain variance exists which is high because all of the probability is at x values (the two box positions) far from the average value of 0. This means a high Heisenberg uncertainty.

If the particle is now allowed to be in each box and the pipe with equal probabilities, then probability is shifted to lower x values and the variance shrinks because the particle is closer to the average value (on average). The authors of (1), however, argue that more uncertainty exists in this case of lower variance because one has less of an idea where the particle is i.e. there is a loss of resolution. They call this counterintuitive. We argue, however, that there seem to be two definitions of uncertainty being used simultaneously. First there is the notion of distance from the average value which is Heisenberg uncertainty and secondly uncertainty due to lack of resolution.

Resolution in Quantum Bound States

Although Heisenberg uncertainty deals with deviations from an average value, resolution uncertainty is important in quantum mechanics because bound states develop humps. These humps often become more numerous and sharper as energy increases. In (2) we argued that increased energy seems to be the price to pay for extra resolution which we called information about the energy eigenstates with lower energies. This information is linked to orthogonality (all energy states are orthonormal) as well as to the possible decay scenarios for a particular bound state. Increased states seem to have higher variances i.e. higher Heisenberg uncertainty, but better resolution i.e. less resolution uncertainty and more information. This we argue is the sense of counterintuitiveness noted in (1). For a Gaussian distribution (e.g. the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution) a higher variance means more uncertainty in position or resolution i.e. it is more difficult to find the particle. Quantum mechanics, however, uses humps which are high resolution regions and so is very different from the classical picture.

Example of a Particle in a Box with Infinite Potential Walls

It is well known that a solution to a particle in a box with infinite potential walls, centered at $x=0$ (i.e. $\langle x \rangle = 0$) and extending to $L/2$ and $-L/2$ is:

$$1/\sqrt{L} \cos(kx) \text{ where } kL/2 = n \cdot 3.14/2 \text{ or } k = n \cdot 3.14/L \text{ for } n \text{ odd} \quad ((2))$$

As n increases, resolution increases. What about Heisenberg uncertainty or the variance?

$$\langle xx \rangle = 1/L \int_{-L/2}^{L/2} x^2 dx \cos(kx)\cos(kx) \quad ((3))$$

Using integration by parts and (3) yields: $1/L \{ L^3/12 + .25 L^3 (-1)^n / (n \cdot 3.14 \cdot 3.14) \}$ ((4)) n odd

This suggests x-variance increases with n.

A similar calculation of this variance is given in (4), but p momentum is retained as a separate variable. The calculation is for a free particle in an infinite potential wall and variance is given as:

$$\left(\frac{L}{2}\right)\left(\frac{L}{2}\right)\left(\frac{L}{2}\right) \left(\frac{1}{3}\right) - 2 / (pp \text{ nn}) \quad ((5))$$

In this case the variance increases with all n if p is independent of n.

Simple Harmonic Oscillator

In (4) the x variance for the simple harmonic oscillator is calculated. The results are given as:

$$n=0 \text{ var}(x) = 1/(2aa) \quad n=1 \text{ var}(x) = 3/(2aa) \text{ and } n=2 \text{ var}(x) = 5/(2aa) \quad ((6)) \quad a=\text{sqrt}(km)$$

Thus resolution increases with increasing n and Heisenberg uncertainty or variance also increases. It may be noted that the classical turning points of the oscillator increase with n and most of the quantum probability lies within these turning points.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that there are two kinds of uncertainties in a quantum bound system. The first is the usual Heisenberg uncertainty measured by variance. This determines whether an x value (or p etc) is close to the average value or not. For a Gaussian an increased variance means more uncertainty as to where the particle is because no “extra” resolution is introduced into the system. As pointed out in (1) if one considers sharp resolutions, one may have high resolution coupled with a high variance. The example used in (1) is that of two boxes joined by a long pipe. If the particle is in either one box or the other with probability $\frac{1}{2}$ then the variance is larger than if the particle is allowed to be in the two boxes and the pipe as well. For the second case, the variance drops because some probability has been shifted to lower x values. The resolution, however, is lower and so it is more difficult to guess where the particle is. The authors of (1) call this counterintuitive.

We argue that a second uncertainty exists namely one linked with resolution. Higher energy levels n seem to lead to more humps i.e. higher resolution. There is less uncertainty in guessing where a particle might be because there are more low probability regions on the sides of the high resolution humps. The variance, however, is greater. Thus there is less resolution uncertainty, but more Heisenberg uncertainty. We examine a particle in a box with infinite potential walls and an oscillator and find that the x variance (Heisenberg uncertainty increases) with n, but resolution increases (i.e. information increases and resolution uncertainty decreases).

References

1. Coles, P.J. et al Entropic Uncertainty Relations and their Applications (2017)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1511.04857.pdf>

2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on Bound Wavefunction Humps as Information (preprint, zendo, 2022)
3. <http://integral-table.com/downloads/single-page-integral-table.pdf>
4. Rabinowitz, M. Quantum and Classical Variance in the Quantum Realm (2007)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/0707.1152.pdf>